

THE USE OF INTERACTIVE AND CONTEXTUAL TEACHING METHODS AS EDUCATIONAL INNOVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the problem of improving the quality of national education necessitates the improvement of educational technologies. The new needs for highly professional specialists cannot be satisfied without a significant restructuring of the professional training system. In this regard, the need to introduce modern teaching technologies into the educational process, developing the creative abilities of students and increasing their interest in mastering the material, is beyond doubt.

The educational process should be fun and effective, i.e. aimed at the maximum achievement of the set goals. As practice shows, the use of active teaching methods allows not only to increase the level of professional training of students, which is the end result of the educational process, but also to make this process more interesting and productive.

Contextual learning is a form of active learning intended for use in higher education, focused on the professional training of students and implemented through the systematic use of the professional context, the gradual saturation of the educational process with elements of professional activity. Contextual learning technology consists of three basic forms of activity: educational activity with the leading role of lectures and seminars; quasi-professional, embodied in games, special courses, special seminars; educational and professional (research work,

industrial practice, real diploma and course design).

Features of the technique

The concept was developed by A.A. Verbitsky in 1991. Contextual learning is based on the theory of activity, according to which the assimilation of social experience is carried out as a result of the active, biased activity of the subject. The following principles are embodied in it: personality activity; problematic; the unity of training and education; sequential modeling in the forms of educational activity of students of the content and conditions of professional activity of specialists. Teaching of general education disciplines is proposed to be interpreted in the context of professional activity, departing in this from the academic presentation of scientific knowledge. As a means of implementing theoretical approaches in contextual learning, it is proposed to fully use the methods of active learning (in the interpretation of A.A.

Verbitsky - methods of contextual learning). At the same time, it is noted that it is necessary to comprehensively approach the use of various forms, methods and means of active learning in an organic combination with traditional methods.

As the results of international studies show, modern Russian students cope well with tasks for the reproduction of knowledge, but find it difficult to apply the acquired knowledge in situations close to life. To achieve modern requirements for learning outcomes, it is necessary to use tasks in which the theoretical content is integrated with practice. The experience of pedagogical activity shows that it is advisable to use the methods and means of contextual learning to solve the indicated tasks.

The essence of contextual learning is defined as the organization of such activities that require the acquisition of new knowledge and their subsequent application, explains and justifies the efforts spent on their assimilation. One of the means of contextual learning that will be most effective in terms of mastering the requirements of the Educational Standard are contextual tasks. A contextual task is a task of a motivational nature, in the condition of which a specific life situation is described, which correlates with the existing socio-cultural experience of students (known, given); the requirement (unknown) of the problem is the analysis, comprehension and explanation of this situation or the choice of a method of action in it, and the result of solving the problem is a meeting with a learning problem and awareness of its personal significance.

Level differentiation of the content of contextual tasks allows setting feasible

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learning tasks for each child, creating an active intellectual background for lessons, fully implementing the principles of scientific character, practical orientation, historicism, and an interdisciplinary approach in teaching.

Today society needs proactive and independent specialists who are able to constantly improve their personality and activities. In classical teaching, tasks are deprived of that life context that gives social significance and personal meaning to the process of cognition, research, search, knowledge does not automatically lead to an understanding of the meaning of life. With the help of contextual tasks, not only subject knowledge and skills are identified, but also their consistency and functionality, independence and creativity of thinking, and other personal characteristics.

An example of contextual learning technology is cognitive instruction. Its essence lies in the presentation of information to the trainee in a symbolic-symbolic, visual-graphic form (texts of books, didactic cards, drawings, diagrams, drawings, tables) for solving educational and cognitive tasks, performing a practice-oriented task, and in some cases for mastering new teaching material.

Cognitive instruction is carried out using guiding texts, the didactic value of which lies in the orientation towards the effective assimilation of knowledge and the formation of competencies. The essence of the guiding text is encoding, storing and communicating to the subject with the help of verbal and symbolic means of relatively similar information of a relatively small volume for individual perception.

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